

About this guide

This guide is intended to help its users develop and evaluate data management and sharing plans (DMSPs).

The structure of the rubric was inspired by the [DART project](#) and the [Support your Data](#) guide. The content was initially compiled and subsequently maintained by members of the Stanford DMP Service.

Using this guide

The six elements included here are each required by the NIH DMS Policy. Though specific format is ostensibly not required, topics within each element were drawn from the [data management and sharing plan templates](#) disseminated by NIH itself.

The categories “incomplete”, “minimally addressed”, and “complete and detailed” are not meant to be evaluative in the sense that they should be construed as some quantitative score. Instead they are meant to assist users identify what part or parts of a data management and sharing plan need additional detail. Data management and sharing are areas replete with jargon, so we’ve added explanatory notes throughout.

Incomplete - Describes an element or topic that requires additional detail.

Minimally Addressed - Describes an element or topic that has been addressed but may benefit from additional information. Because the DMS Policy has been implemented only for a short time (and we have not had DMSPs returned yet), the criteria for what may fall under this category may change over time.

Complete and Detailed - Describes an element or topic that has been fully addressed and may even be described in greater detail than is necessarily required in the data management and sharing plan.

Element 1: Data Type

This section of the plan should include a general summary of the types and estimated amount of scientific data to be generated and/or used in the research. Data should be described in general terms that address the size, data modality (e.g., imaging, genomic, mobile, survey), level of aggregation (e.g., individual, aggregated, summarized), and/or the degree of data processing (i.e., how raw or processed the data will be) for each type of data.

This section includes three topics.

1	Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
A	Types and amount of scientific data expected to be generated in the project.	The list of data types that will be generated over the course of the project is incomplete.	A list of the types of scientific data that will be generated over the course of the project is given, but details about formats, approximate sizes, or other relevant details are not.	All of the different types of scientific data that will be generated are listed along with their formats, approximate sizes, and any other relevant details.
B	Scientific data that will be preserved and shared, and the rationale for doing so.	The description of data that will be preserved and/or shared is incomplete.	The data (and related materials) that will be preserved or made available is described but not the rationale for why that data specifically.	All of the different types of scientific data that will be preserved and/or shared is listed as well as the rationale for why it makes sense to preserve/share those specific forms of data.
C	Metadata, other relevant data, and associated documentation.	The description of metadata/other materials needed to make use of shared data is incomplete.	Metadata/other important materials are mentioned but not described.	All of the metadata and other materials needed to make use of shared data are described in detail.

NOTES

- This section can be written in narrative format but, especially for the content expected under 1A and 1B, tables might be more straightforward for projects involving a number of complex data types.
- “Preservation” vs “sharing” has proven to be a tricky distinction so far, especially since repositories can be used for both.
 - **Preservation** in this context roughly refers to long term storage for a wide array of research materials and products (including datasets) that may or may not be made available to others.
 - **Sharing** in this context roughly refers to making research materials and products available for use by others. This does not *necessarily* mean they’re available to anyone for any purpose (i.e. “open” data sharing) - the DMS policy allows for restricted forms of data sharing.
 - In terms of what data should be shared, it is whatever underlies research findings. Most typically being those that are described in research publications.
 - Almost certainly more data will need to be preserved than shared. A researcher may preserve data in its raw form and then share a cleaned/processed/analyzed form, for example. An important element to this section is explaining why data that is going to be preserved should be preserved, why data that is going to be shared should be shared, etc.
 - **Metadata** in this context roughly just refers to information/materials related to the data that is needed to make use of the data. Common forms of “metadata” in this context include things like data dictionaries, codebooks, protocols, etc. Typically these things can be submitted alongside permanent datasets in a repository.

Element 2: Related Tools, Software, and Code

This section of the plan should give an indication of whether specialized tools are needed to access or manipulate shared scientific data to support replication or reuse, and name(s) of the needed tool(s) and software.

2	Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
A	The software/code needed to make use of the data.	<p>If specific software tools (e.g. proprietary tools needed to open specific file types) will be needed, the list is incomplete.</p> <p>If specialized tools are not needed, this is not mentioned.</p> <p>If custom code will be generated, the details about its characteristics (e.g. programming language used) and how it will be made available (if possible) are not addressed.</p>	<p>If specialized software tools will be needed, only the names of these tools are given.</p> <p>If specialized tools will not be needed, no additional information is provided about why this is the case (i.e. use of common file formats).</p> <p>If custom code will be generated, details about its characteristics (e.g. the programming language that will be used) and how it will be made available (if possible) are addressed, but no information is given about how dependencies and other details will be communicated.</p>	<p>If specialized software tools will be needed, their names and how they can be acquired are given.</p> <p>If specialized tools will not be needed, the reason why is given. Examples of tools that can be used to open and use the data are given (e.g. Excel, SPSS, etc).</p> <p>If custom code is going to be generated, details about its characteristics and how it will be made available are given. The methods by which information related to the exact versions, libraries, dependencies, etc that will be used will ultimately be communicated is given.</p>

NOTES

- Because the DMSP reflects proposed practices at the time it is written (i.e. before the start of the proposed project), it is unlikely that every detail about the use of specific software tools, custom code, etc will be known. This section does not need to include all of these details. The focus should be on:
 - If particular types of data require the use of particular computational tools, what those tools are and how they can be accessed by other researchers.
 - Plans related to sharing custom code.
- An important reminder here that **HYPERLINKS SHOULD NOT BE EMBEDDED INTO DMSPs**. If software is to be made available via a Github repository or similar, that fact should be mentioned (and the repository name should be given), but a URL is not appropriate.
- Ideally, researchers should archive pertinent Github repositories via Zenodo to ensure there is a timestamped and citable version. But NIH has also included Github on lists of acceptable places to store code. So...
- There is no expectation in the DMS policy that custom code or other software created as part of the analysis process be made available to others. We can encourage it, however.
- There is no expectation that the software tools mentioned in this section should be openly or freely available. If a piece of proprietary software is needed to make use of shared data, then that just needs to be noted in the plan.
- If the data is in a common or open (i.e. non-proprietary) file format and therefore does not need specialized software, that fact should be - pending more guidance from NIH - mentioned in the DMSP.

Element 3: Standards

This section should give an indication of what standards will be applied to the scientific data and associated metadata (i.e., data formats, data dictionaries, data identifiers, definitions, unique identifiers, and other data documentation).

3	Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
A	Any common data standards/standardized practices applied to the data	<p>If formal data standards have been developed and widely adopted for a particular data type (and will be used in the proposed research), they are not mentioned or described.</p> <p>If applicable formal data standards have not been developed and/or widely adopted for a particular data type, then the practices and strategies that will be implemented to ensure usability/interoperability of datasets are not mentioned or described.</p>	<p>If formal data standards have been developed and widely adopted for a particular data type (and will be used in the proposed research), they are mentioned by name but not described.</p> <p>If applicable formal data standards have not been developed and/or widely adopted for a particular data type, that fact is mentioned but the practices that will be implemented to ensure usability and/or interoperability are not described.</p>	<p>Applicable formal data standards are mentioned and described</p> <p>If applicable formal data standards have not been developed and/or widely adopted for a particular data type, the practices that will be implemented to ensure usability and/or interoperability are fully described.</p>

NOTES

- This section is, far and away, what we get the most questions about. In simple terms, a **data standard** can be thought of as an agreed upon set of rules about how data should be organized, described, etc. What NIH seems generally to be referring to is less particular file formats (e.g. fastq, dicom, etc) and more things like common data elements, data models, and other standardized practices for organizing and representing data (e.g. the BIDS standard for neuroimaging data).
- If a formal data standard does not exist for a particular type of data/metadata, then that also should be noted in the plan. Because standards are developed to aid in usability and interoperability, we recommend giving additional information about related practices and strategies as an alternative.
 - In this context, **interoperability** generally refers to the degree to which a dataset can be combined with other data, read and acted upon by software tools, and included research workflows.
 - **Usability** is a less formal version of interoperability, loosely summed up by “Could another researcher open up these files and make use of them?”
- In the absence of formal data standards, we’ve been recommending that researchers discuss how they’ll be standardizing practices within the research group (shared protocols, use the same variable names across files, maintenance of documentation, etc).

Element 4: Data Preservation, Access, and Associated Timelines

This section of the plan should detail plans and timelines for how data will be preserved and made accessible to others. This section includes three topics.

4	Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
A	Repository where scientific data and metadata will be archived	<p>If deposited in a repository, this is mentioned but the name of the repository is not given.</p> <p>If not, alternative methods for archiving and making data available are not discussed.</p>	<p>If deposited in a repository: the name of a repository is given, but additional details are not given.</p> <p>If not, the rationale for not depositing in a repository is discussed but alternative methods for archiving data and making data available are not given (or vice versa).</p>	<p>If deposited in a repository, the name of the repository and additional details (e.g. how data is preserved) are given.</p> <p>If not, alternative methods for preserving and making data available are described and the rationale for choosing these methods is given.</p>
B	How scientific data will be findable and identifiable	Not mentioned.	Particular mechanisms for sharing data (repository, request, etc) are mentioned. But the precise methods needed to ensure findability (DOIs, metadata, etc) are not.	<p>If data is deposited into a repository, the precise methods used to ensure findability/identifiability are described.</p> <p>If data is not deposited into a repository, alternative mechanisms for accessing the data (even if heavily restricted) are outlined.</p>
C	When and how long the scientific data will be made available	Not mentioned.	Addresses when but not for how long (or vice versa) data will be made available.	Addresses when and for how long every type of data will be made available.

NOTES

- The NIH DMS Policy states that data should be made available at the time of publication or the end of the grant period, whichever comes first.
- NIH and Stanford both require that data be kept for *at least* three years following project closeout, but both entities encourage researchers to make scientific data available for as long as they anticipate it being useful for the larger research community, the broader public, and other stakeholders.
- The use of repositories are encouraged, but they may not be appropriate under all circumstances.
- Not all of the data associated with a particular project or paper needs to be deposited into the same repository. A statement about how the persistent identifiers/URLs for all datasets shared in a repository will be cited in a relevant paper would be a good inclusion to this section.
- We have language that can be used for SDR, Dryad, and Vivli. For language for other, specialized, repositories, see [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org).

Element 5: Access, Distribution, or Reuse Considerations

This section of the plan should describe any applicable factors affecting subsequent access, distribution, or reuse of scientific data. In particular, factors such as informed consent, privacy and confidentiality protections, and restrictions imposed by federal, Tribal, or state laws, regulations, or policies, or existing or anticipated agreements should be described.

This section includes three topics.

5	Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
A	Factors affecting subsequent access, distribution, or reuse of scientific data	<p>If data sharing will not need to be restricted, this is not mentioned.</p> <p>If data sharing will need to be restricted, the specific factors affecting subsequent access are not described (e.g. "Data can not be shared").</p>	<p>If data sharing will not need to be restricted, this is mentioned but the rationale (i.e. the research does not involve human participants) is not.</p> <p>If data sharing will need to be restricted, the specific factors affecting subsequent access are described but the steps that will be taken to provide some sort of access (if possible) (i.e. to deidentified versions, aggregated data, DUAs, etc) are not discussed.</p>	<p>If data sharing will not be restricted, the rationale is given.</p> <p>If data sharing will need to be restricted, the specific factors affecting subsequent access are described in detail and the steps that will be taken to provide some form of access (if possible) are discussed in detail.</p>
B	Whether access to scientific data will be controlled	Not mentioned.	<p>If controls will not be needed, this is mentioned but the rationale (i.e. the research does not involve human participants) is not.</p>	<p>If controls will not be needed, the rationale is given.</p> <p>If controls will be needed, the process by which access will be granted and to whom is</p>

			If controls will be needed, this fact is mentioned but how access will be granted and to whom is not discussed.	outlined.
C	Protections for privacy, rights, and confidentiality of human research participants	Not mentioned.	If protections will be needed: this fact is mentioned, but the specifics of what those protections are and how they will be applied are not.	If protections will not be needed, the specifics of what those protections and how they will be applied are detailed.

NOTES

- This is where researchers can list any factors that restrict their ability to share data.
 - For some research projects, especially those that don't work with data derived from human participants, there may be no such factors.
 - The DMS policy is not an open data mandate. Restrictions can be indicated as long as they can be justified.
- Acceptable reasons for restricting data sharing:
 - Informed consent will not permit or will limit the scope or extent of sharing.
 - Existing consent prohibits sharing or limits the scope or extent of sharing.
 - Privacy or safety of research participants would be compromised.
 - Explicit federal, state, local, or Tribal law, regulation, or policy prohibits disclosure.
 - Datasets cannot practically be digitized with reasonable efforts.
- A limited number of repositories (all typically specialized, many funded by NIH themselves) allow for controlled access. If any of the following is true, a researcher should consider controlling access:
 - There are explicit limits places on subsequent use (i.e. by laws, policies, informed consent, etc)
 - The data could be considered sensitive.
 - The data can not be deidentified sufficiently to mitigate the rise of re identification.
- NIH gives the following best practices for protecting participant privacy:
 - Ensure appropriate deidentification
 - Establish data sharing and use agreements
 - Understand legal protections against disclosure and misuse.

Element 6: Oversight of Data Management and Sharing

This section of the plan should indicate how compliance with the plan will be monitored and managed, frequency of oversight, and by whom.

We have some sample language for this section.

Topic	Incomplete	Minimally Addressed	Complete and Detailed
How will compliance be monitored, by whom, and what is their degree of expertise.	Incomplete information is given about who will be responsible for ensuring compliance	The person(s) responsible for ensuring compliance is named, but no details are given about how compliance will be monitored.	The person(s) responsible for ensuring compliance is named and details about how compliance will be monitored are included.

NOTES

- Some of the sample DMSPs provided by NIH include a statement about an office on campus tasked with monitoring compliance with the contents of DMSPs. Stanford has no such office (neither does any other university as far as we know). So the responsibility ultimately falls to the PI on the grant.
- For grants written by a junior researcher who will be supervised by other PIs, we recommend that the researcher indicate that they will do everything “under the mentorship of Dr(s). [insert senior PIs name]”.